

Sintering and mechanical behaviour of CeO₂ doped ZrO₂ ceramics

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The sintering behaviour of commercial grade zirconia powder containing varying amount of CeO₂ has been studied at different temperatures (1400 to 1500°C). The bulk density for each composition was found to increase in general with the increasing temperature and a maximum density was achieved at 1500°C in each case. Phase estimation was done by XRD and corroborated by Raman spectroscopy. The amount of tetragonal phase increased with increasing CeO₂ content and the 14 mol% CeO₂-ZrO₂ produced 100% tetragonal phase. The effect of CeO₂ content on fracture toughness and strength was also examined. Fracture toughness decreased with increasing ceria content whereas bending strength increased upto 12.3 mol% and then decreased.

Aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) bioceramic has been widely used in orthopaedic surgery for more than 30 years as femoral head in hip joint prosthesis because of its combination of high strength, excellent corrosion resistance, low friction and high wear resistance¹. Recently zirconium oxide has also emerged as another ceramic material having potential for application in hip joint prosthesis. The interest in zirconia (ZrO₂) ceramics derives from its high fracture toughness and tensile strength². These improved properties make it possible to manufacture femoral heads for total hip prostheses that are smaller than the present generation of Al₂O₃ heads. Pure zirconia cannot be used for manufacturing any ceramic product due to volume change associated with transition from tetragonal to monoclinic form during cooling resulting in shattering of the product during sintering.

Most of the work to date on CeO₂ doped ZrO₂ ceramics has involved the use of high purity fine powder prepared either by coprecipitation or by hydrolysis technique to achieve a dense fine grained material. The information available in the literature with regard to CeO₂ content and the sintering temperature for the development of 100% t-phase in CeO₂-ZrO₂ ceramics are contradictory.

The aim of this investigation is to study the sintering and mechanical behaviour of commercial grade zirconia powder containing varying amount of CeO₂ at 1400 to 1500°C. Based on the study, the promising composition and optimum temperature would be selected to produce dense Ce-TZP ceramics with better mechanical properties.

Results and discussion

The specimen composition, sintering temperature, bulk

density and shrinkage for the CeO₂-ZrO₂ ceramics are listed in Table 1. From 1400 to 1450°C, the bulk density increased significantly for 9.1 to 12.3 mol% CeO₂ but in case of 14 mol% CeO₂ it remained unchanged; however at 1500°C it increased from 6.02 to 6.24 g cm⁻³. The bulk density for a particular composition was found to increase in general with the increasing temperature and a maximum density was achieved at 1500°C in each case.

Table 1. Sintered properties of ceria-doped zirconia ceramics

Sample code	Sintering temp. (°C)	Open porosity (%)	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Shrinkage (%)
CePSZ (9.1 mol% CeO ₂)	1400	0	5.86	–
	1450	0	6.00	–
	1500	0	6.05	21.6
CePSZ (10.7 mol% CeO ₂)	1400	3.5	5.65	–
	1450	0	6.03	–
	1500	0	6.12	20.6
CePSZ (12.3 mol% CeO ₂)	1400	4.9	5.63	–
	1450	0	6.10	–
	1500	0	6.21	21.3
CePSZ (14.0 mol% CeO ₂)	1400	0	6.02	–
	1450	0	6.02	–
	1500	0	6.24	22.0

Since the aim of the present study was to produce dense Ce-TZP ceramics with better mechanical properties, only the specimens sintered at 1500°C which resulted in maximum density were used for further characterization.

The XRD pattern of as-sintered surface shows peaks at 28.3 (11 $\bar{1}$) and 31.56 (111), indicating the presence of monoclinic phase in all the samples except 14 mol% CeO₂. The occurrence of peak at 30.3 (111) as well as the characteristic splittings of peaks such as (002) (200), (202) (220), (113) (311) and (004) (400) revealed the presence of tetragonal phase in all the samples⁴. XRD patterns showed that sample containing 14 mol% CeO₂ contained only tetragonal phase and no monoclinic or cubic phase. Since the (111) reflections of cubic and tetragonal phase are coincident, the findings of XRD for this particular composition was corroborated by Raman spectroscopy as recommended by Srinivasan *et al.*⁵.

From factor group analysis only one Raman active band is anticipated for cubic zirconia and the absence of 625 cm⁻¹ band, which is characteristic of the cubic symmetry, demonstrated that this sample consisted of only tetragonal phase⁶. The group theory for the tetragonal phase predicts six Raman active bands in the region 100–700 cm⁻¹. According to the group theory prediction we expected five Raman bands in the region 200–700 cm⁻¹ covered in the present case, but we observed six Raman bands in this region. The bands were located at 252, 314, 370, 402, 459 and 632 cm⁻¹ and were assigned to the tetragonal phase. Except 370 cm⁻¹ band, other bands observed in our case is very much comparable with those reported by Hirata *et al.* who reported bands at 148, 249, 304, 411, 461 and 621 cm⁻¹ for tetragonal phase for ZrO₂-12 mol% CeO₂. Phillipi and Mazdiyasi have reported nine bands whereas Hirata *et al.* and Ishigane *et al.* reported six bands for tetragonal phase in the 100–700 cm⁻¹ region⁷. There was no agreement on the frequencies of bands reported by these workers⁷. The discrepancy in the number and positions of bands may be attributed to some modification of crystal structure in the specimen.

A quantitative estimation of as-sintered ceramics by XRD revealed that the amount of tetragonal phase increased with increasing CeO₂ content and the 14 mol% CeO₂-ZrO₂ produced 100% tetragonal phase. The fraction of tetragonal and monoclinic phases in the as-sintered ceramics (fired at 1500°C) as a function of the CeO₂ content is shown in Fig. 1(a). For 9.1, 10.7, 12.3 and 14.0 mol% the amount of tetragonal phase was 88.07, 92.0, 97.86 and 100.0% and the amount of monoclinic phase was 11.93, 8.0, 2.14 and 0.0% respectively. In the fractured sample the monoclinic phase content increased to 75.45, 56.08 and 9.45 for 9.1, 10.7 and 12.3 mol% respectively and for 14.0 mol%, monoclinic phase content remained unchanged.

The fraction of tetragonal and monoclinic phases on the

Fig. 1(a). The fraction of tetragonal and monoclinic phases as a function of CeO₂ content on as-sintered surface.

Fig. 1(b). The fraction of tetragonal and monoclinic phases as a function of CeO₂ content on the fractured surface.

fractured surface as estimated by XRD is shown in Fig. 1(b). From the quantitative estimation of monoclinic phase in the as-sintered and fractured surface it is seen that the amount of monoclinic phase formed by stress-induced transformation decreased with increasing CeO₂ content. Stress-induced transformed monoclinic phase for 9.1, 10.7 and 12.3 mol% CeO₂ content was 63.52, 48.08 and 7.30% respectively. The amount of monoclinic phase remained unchanged before and after fracture in case of 14.0 mol% CeO₂ content indicating that no $t \rightarrow m$ transformation had taken place. The fracture strength value for 9.1 mol% CeO₂ was 375 MPa and this value increased to a maximum value of 470 MPa for 12.3 mol% CeO₂; thereafter it decreased to 402 MPa for 14.0 mol% CeO₂. The result indicates that fracture strength increases with increase in ceria concentration upto 12.3 mol% and then decreases with further increase in ceria concentration. This trend signifies that fracture strength is not controlled by stress-induced transformation toughening alone which is contrary to the observation made by Sharma *et al.*⁸. It has been reported that crystallite size of ceria-zirconia composite ceramics decreases with increase in ceria concentration⁹. In the present case the fracture strength upto 12.3 mol% CeO₂

seems to be strongly dependent on grain size of the composite ceramics. Tsukuma *et al.*¹⁰ have also reported that fracture strength of ceria-zirconia composite upto 10.0 mol% ceria depended on grain size. The strength values of CeO₂ doped ZrO₂ as published in literature vary considerably and this may be attributed to the starting powder of varying characteristics resulting from different powder preparation methods. Sharma *et al.* by using spray dried powder achieved a value of 730 MPa for 12.0 mol% CeO₂⁸. The relatively lower value in our case may be attributed mainly to the commercial grade powder prepared by conventional method as it is well known that the initial powder characteristics have a large influence on the final properties of sintered product. Fracture toughness decreased with increasing CeO₂ content and a maximum value of 10.8 MPa. \sqrt{m} was achieved for ceria-zirconia ceramics containing 9.1 mol% CeO₂. The dependence of fracture toughness on CeO₂ content corresponded to the amount of monoclinic phase formed by stress-induced transformation as shown in Fig. 1(b). A decreased CeO₂ content and increased grain size is reported to result in an increased transformability of tetragonal phase and concomitant increased fracture toughness¹⁰.

Experimental

Zirconia powders containing 9.1, 10.7, 12.3 and 14.0 mol% CeO₂ were prepared using commercial grade zirconia (Indian Rare Earth, ZrO₂ 98.0%; Fe₂O₃ 0.07%; TiO₂ 0.16%; SiO₂ 0.25%; L.O.I. 1.50%; phase content 100% monoclinic) and Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O (Aldrich Chemical Company, USA). The required amount of ZrO₂ and Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O for each composition was ground in a planetary mill, dried and calcined at 500°C for 3 h. The calcined product was reground in isopropanol and polyvinyl alcohol was added during grinding. These powders were uniaxially pressed into plates and bar at 120 MPa. The green compacts were sintered at 1400 to 1500°C for 2 h in air.

The bulk density of the sintered body was measured by the water displacement method. Measurement of three-point bending strength was performed using a 30 mm span and a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm min⁻¹ in an Instron, model 1185. Phase identification was done by XRD and corroborated

by Raman spectroscopy. The tetragonal phase content was determined from ratio of intensity of the (111) tetragonal peak to combined intensity of the (111) and (11 $\bar{1}$) monoclinic peaks plus the (111) tetragonal peak. The fracture toughness was determined by single edge notched bar method.

Conclusion :

The present study showed that sintering at 1500°C resulted in maximum density for each composition. The amount of tetragonal phase increased with increasing ceria content. Fracture toughness was dependent on CeO₂ content and the value decreased with increasing CeO₂ content. Bending strength increased with increasing CeO₂ content upto 12.3 mol% CeO₂ and then decreased. Since cortical bone has a bending strength of 50–150 MPa and fracture toughness of 2–12 MPa \sqrt{m} , ZrO₂-10.7 mol% CeO₂ ceramic sintered at 1500°C having a bending strength of 430 MPa and fracture toughness of 9.5 MPa. \sqrt{m} may be considered suitable for making femoral ball in total hip prosthesis if otherwise found suitable.

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